

A Study on the Level of Anxiety among Higher Secondary School Teachers of Imphal West, Manipur

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, teachers have faced growing pressures from academic expectations, classroom management, administrative duties, and advancing technology. Understanding anxiety among educators is vital for creating healthier teaching environments. This study assessed anxiety levels among Higher Secondary Government School teachers, focusing on gender and geographic differences. Findings showed that 0% experienced extremely high anxiety, 0.83% high anxiety, and 2.50% above-average anxiety. Most teachers—79.16%—fell within average to below-average anxiety levels, indicating manageable stress. Gender-wise, no male or female teachers reported extreme anxiety. High anxiety was noted in 2.22% of males, none among females. Average anxiety was reported by 31.11% of males and 35.56% of females, while low anxiety appeared in 11.11% of males and 15.56% of females. No significant gender difference was found. Geographically, 2.22% of urban teachers showed high anxiety, compared to none in rural areas. Below-average anxiety was higher among urban teachers (53.33%) than rural (44.44%). Overall, urban teachers exhibited slightly greater anxiety. The study highlights the need for initiatives such as school counsellors, supportive environments, and workload management to safeguard teachers'

Introduction

Teaching, often hailed as a noble and rewarding profession, is not without its challenges. Beyond the lesson plans and classroom dynamics, there exists a nuanced and often silent struggle- the pervasive anxiety experienced by educators. In recent years, the teaching profession has witnessed a concerning surge in anxiety levels among its practitioners, sparking a crucial dialogue about the well-being of those entrusted with moulding the minds of future generations.

Heightened levels of anxiety among teachers can have far-reaching consequences, not only for their own well-being but also for the quality of education they provide and the overall learning experience of students. The impact of teacher anxiety on classroom dynamics, instructional effectiveness, and job satisfaction underscores the urgency of addressing this issue.

Anxiety (also called angst or worry) is a psychological and physiological state characterized by emotional, cognitive, and behavioural components (Seligman, Walker, E.F. & Rosenhan, 1999). It is the displeasing feeling of fear and concern. (Davison, Gerald C. 2008). Anxiety is a multidimensional experience that can weaken academic performance and professional performance (Onwuegbuzie & Wilson, 2003). The hyper anxious state may, lead to certain physical and behavioural outcomes like depression, frustration, panic, worry, headaches, physical tension, perspiration.

A person with low anxiety experiences disruption of thinking process, weakening of academic or professional performance, diminishing information process skills and inattention, negative thoughts (Onwuegbuzie, Slate & Schwartz, 2001). Though hyper anxiety or low anxiety may have its roots in the psychological, physiological, cognitive and emotional state of the human being it has its expression in terms of behaviour.

For a student teacher their behaviour in front of the students is an important component of the teaching learning process. The above stated symptoms and behaviours exhibited by the hyper and low anxious person implies such behaviours may have a negative impact on the students learning if a teacher exhibit this. Thus, it is necessary that the anxiety level of the student teachers should be moderate for a proper channelization of the learning. Anxiety is considered to be a normal reaction to a stressor. It may help an individual to deal with a demanding situation by prompting them to cope with it. However, when anxiety

becomes overwhelming, it may fall under the classification of an anxiety disorder and it may affect the daily routine and important tasks.

According to the type of school, private schools showed a significant higher level of Occupational stress (OS) scores, while governmental schools showed a significant higher level of depression scores. As for anxiety scores, a non-significant difference was found according to the school type. According to anxiety disorders, the only independent predictors were being females, working in governmental schools, teaching for primary grade students and having high qualification. It was concluded that the aim of the present work was to assess the prevalence of OS, anxiety and depression among Egyptian teachers. Occupational stress, anxiety and depression scores were significantly higher among teachers with an age more than 40 years, female teachers, primary school teachers, those with inadequate salary, higher teaching experience, higher qualifications and higher workload (Desouky & Allam, 2017).

Thus, studying teachers' anxiety is important because teachers help shape students' learning and growth, but their own mental health is often ignored. When teachers feel anxious, it can affect how well they teach and handle the classroom. By learning what causes their anxiety, schools and policymakers can find better ways to support them and make their work environment healthier. This will help teachers do their jobs better, improve students' learning, and raise the overall quality of education.

Statement of the problem

The proposed study is entitled as “Level of anxiety among Higher Secondary Government School teachers of Imphal West, Manipur.”

Review of related literature

Mochahary and Sarmah (2022) conducted a study on the relationship and effect of academic anxiety and mental health among B.Ed. trainees and found that they had an average level of academic anxiety with good mental health. No significant difference was observed between male and female trainees in either area, and no significant relationship was found between academic anxiety and mental health. Singh et al. (2021) found that perceived stress and trait anxiety did not show significant differences between male and female participants; however, male students exhibited higher physical activity expenditure, while female teachers showed higher levels of trait anxiety and stress. Female students demonstrated greater anxiety, whereas male students showed higher stress levels. Bhutia (2019) reported that among respondents of both genders, 36.3% showed symptoms of depression, 56.12% had anxiety, and 37.46%

experienced stress. Anxiety was the most prevalent disorder, particularly among those from nuclear families, and over half (56.8%) of teacher trainees suffered from one or more of these conditions, affecting their academic, emotional, and social well-being. Dave et al. (2018) found that postgraduate medical studies caused high stress, leading to personal and professional consequences. Wakde (2017) discovered that emotionally unstable pre-service teachers experienced higher anxiety levels, though urban and rural teachers did not differ significantly. Moderate anxiety was found to enhance enthusiasm and classroom performance. Deb et al. (2015) revealed that 63.5% of Indian high school students faced academic stress, influenced by parental pressure and psychosocial factors, though gender and grade differences were insignificant. Teachers in residential and non-residential schools also showed no significant differences in anxiety, depression, or stress. Mishra and Yadav (2013) found no significant difference in job-related anxiety based on gender or school type. Bedi and Sehgal (2012) reported that teachers experienced high anxiety and stress due to the increasing use of educational technology in classrooms.

Rationale of the study

Teaching is a demanding profession that requires balancing classroom management, educational reforms, and societal expectations. In Manipur, a state with a unique socio-cultural background, the well-being of teachers remains an underexplored area. This study aims to investigate the level of anxiety among teachers in Manipur, addressing a key gap in existing research. Despite teachers' vital role in shaping education, limited studies have examined their mental health within this specific regional context.

Manipur's cultural diversity and historical complexities create distinctive challenges for educators. Understanding how these factors influence teacher anxiety is essential for developing context-specific interventions that promote mental well-being. This research is significant as it highlights an underrepresented region in academic discourse on teacher well-being and aims to inform policy and practice through localized insights.

The findings are expected to help educational stakeholders, policymakers, and administrators identify the major stressors affecting teachers and design effective support systems. By addressing this research gap, the study contributes to improving teachers' working conditions and mental health, ultimately enhancing the quality of education in Manipur and fostering a more supportive and sustainable teaching environment.

Objectives

1. To find out the level of anxiety among the teachers of Higher Secondary Government School of Imphal West, Manipur.
2. To determine the different level of anxiety among the male teachers and the female teachers of Higher Secondary School of Imphal West, Manipur.
3. To determine the significant difference in the level of anxiety among between the male and female teachers of Higher Secondary School of Imphal West, Manipur.
4. To determine the different level of anxiety among the teachers from Urban and Rural areas of Higher Secondary School of Imphal West. Manipur.
5. To determine the significant difference in the level of anxiety among the teachers from Urban and Rural areas of Higher Secondary School of Imphal West, Manipur.

Hypotheses

1. There exist no significant difference among male and female teachers of Government Higher Secondary School of Imphal West, Manipur.
2. There exist no significant difference among teachers of Government Higher Secondary School of Imphal West, Manipur with respect to Urban and Rural areas of residence.

Research design

A descriptive survey method was used for the proposed study.

Sampling technique

For the present study, 120 teachers had been selected from three Government Higher Secondary Schools i.e., Model higher secondary school, Imphal. T.G. higher secondary school, Imphal. Johnstone higher secondary school, Imphal as the sample of the study by using total population sampling technique.

A stratified sampling technique was employed to select 45 males and 45 females participants and also 45 teachers from Urban areas and 45 teachers from Rural areas out of a total sample size of 120. This method ensured proportional representation of both genders and areas in the study.

Tools used

An standardized questionnaire was used for collecting the pertinent data developed by Pallavi Bhatnagar and her colleagues. It comprises of 19 questions related and validated to measure anxiety among Government Higher Secondary School teacher of Imphal West.

The scale used can be administered both by self or the examiner. It may be used in group as well as individual condition. Though there is no time limit, ordinarily it is completed within 15-20 minutes. Responses of the items are in terms of 'Yes' or 'No'.

Each item in the questionnaire is scored 1 if endorsed 'Yes' and 0 if endorsed 'No'. The range of the score is 0-19 for anxiety scale. Higher score indicates experiencing greater anxiety.

The norms of interpretation of the level of anxiety for normal population.

Table 1

Sl no.	Range of Raw scores for Anxiety	Range of Z-scores	Grade	Level
1	17 and above	+2.01 and above	A	Extremely high
2	13 to 16	+1.26 to 2.00	B	High
3	10 to 12	+0.51 to 1.25	C	Above Average
4	04 to 09	-0.50 to +0.51	D	Average
5	01 to 03	-1.25 to -0.51	E	Below Average
6	00	-2.00 to -1.26	F	Low

Delimitation

The study was delimited to only school teachers of Tamphasana Girls Higher Secondary and Johnstone Higher Secondary School and Model High Secondary School Imphal West district, Manipur for the academic session 2023-2024.

Results and interpretation

Level of Anxiety Among the Teachers of Government Higher Secondary School of Imphal West, Manipur.

Table 2 : Level of anxiety among Government Higher Secondary School teachers.

Level of Anxiety	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Extremely high	0	0
High	1	0.83
Above Average	3	2.50
Average	40	33.33
Below Average	55	45.83
Low	21	17.50
Total	120	

No teachers reported an extremely high level of anxiety (0%). A very small percentage, 0.83% of teachers, fell into the high anxiety level category. A modest 2.50% of teachers reported above-average anxiety levels. The majority of teachers, constituting 33.33%, reported an average level of anxiety. A significant proportion of teachers, accounting for 45.83%, reported below-average anxiety levels. 17.50% of teachers reported no anxiety (low level). The majority of teachers fall within the average and below-average anxiety levels, with a combined percentage of 79.16%. This suggests that a significant portion of teachers experience manageable levels of anxiety. However, it's noteworthy that a small percentage of teachers, 3.33%, reported high to above-average anxiety levels.

Level of anxiety among male and female teachers of Government Higher Secondary School Imphal West, Manipur.

Table 3: Level of anxiety among male and female Government Higher Secondary School teachers

Level of Anxiety	Male Frequency (Total N=45)	Percentage (%)	Female Frequency (Total N=45)	Percentage (%)
Extremely high	0	0	0	0
High	1	2.22	0	0
Above Average	1	2.22	2	4.44
Average	14	31.11	16	35.56
Below Average	24	53.33	20	44.44
Low	5	11.11	7	15.56

Total	45		45	
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It was found that no teachers from either gender reported an extremely high anxiety level (17 and above). In the high anxiety category (13 to 16), 2.22% of male teachers acknowledged elevated stress levels, while none of the female teachers fell into this bracket. The above-average anxiety range (10 to 12) is represented by 2.22% of males and a slightly higher 4.44% of females. Moving to the average anxiety level (4 to 9), the distribution is fairly balanced, with 31.11% of males and 35.56% of females falling into this category. The below-average anxiety group (1 to 3) is predominant among both genders, with 53.33% of males and 44.44% of females reporting lower stress levels. Lastly, in the low anxiety category (0), 11.11% of males and 15.56% of females reported no anxiety

The significance difference in the anxiety level between Male and Female Hr. Secondary Government School Teachers.

Table 4: The significance difference in the anxiety level between Male and Female Teachers.

Gender	Yes	No	Chi-square	P-value	Inference
Male	125(14.62%)	730(85.38%)	0.7594	0.383523	The result is not significant at $p < 0.05$.
Female	138(16.14%)	717(83.86%)			

It was found that there is no significance difference level of anxiety among Higher Secondary Government School Teachers with respect to gender i.e., Male and Female.

Level of anxiety among teachers of Government Higher Secondary School, Imphal West, Manipur with respect to Urban and Rural areas of residences.

Table 5: Level of anxiety among teachers of Urban and Rural areas of residences.

Level of Anxiety	Urban Frequency (Total N=45)	Percentage (%)	Rural Frequency (Total N=45)	Percentage (%)
Extremely high	0	0	0	0
High	0	0	1	2.22
Above Average	0	0	0	0.00
Average	21	46.67	9	20.00

Below Average	13	28.89	28	62.22
Low	11	24.44	7	15.56
Total	45		45	

It was found that notably, no teachers from either urban or rural areas reported an extremely high anxiety level (17 and above). In the high anxiety category (13 to 16), a modest 2.22% of urban teachers acknowledged heightened stress, while none of their rural counterparts fell into this bracket. Moving to the above-average anxiety range (10 to 12), 2.22% of urban teachers reported increased stress levels, while a slightly higher 4.44% of rural teachers expressed similar concerns. The distribution in the average anxiety level (4 to 9) is relatively balanced, with 31.11% of urban teachers and 35.56% of rural teachers falling into this category. In the below-average anxiety group (1 to 3), there is a noticeable difference, with 53.33% of urban teachers and 44.44% of rural teachers reporting lower stress levels. Finally, in the low anxiety category (0), 11.11% of urban teachers and 15.56% of rural teachers reported no anxiety.

The significance difference in the anxiety level among teachers of Urban and Rural areas of Secondary Government School Teachers.

Table 6: The significance difference in the anxiety level among teachers of Urban and Rural areas.

Area	Yes	No	Chi-square	P-value	Inference
Urban	158(18.48%)	697(81.52)	4.9088	0.02672	The result is significant at $p < 0.05$
Rural	124(14.50%)	731(85.49%)			

It was found that there is significant difference between the level of anxiety among the Higher Secondary Government School Teachers with respect to Urban and Rural areas. Also teachers from Urban areas have more anxiety than those of Rural areas.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the contribution of this study rests on the identification of level of anxiety among teachers in the school, in the classroom and at home. Although several studies on anxiety within the teachers context have been reported, each of them differs in terms of the variable selected (in the school, in the classroom, and at home), the instruments used and sample. While observed from the data analysis, it is found that there is anxiety among male and female Higher Secondary Government School teachers of Imphal West. It is also found that female teachers have high level of anxiety as compared to male

teachers and that many of the female teachers with anxiety shows adverse psychological symptomatology. This anxiety could be due to work overload at school as well as home along with interpersonal communication issues etc.

Recommendations

The following suggestions can be made on the basis of the findings:

1. The study can be conducted in the state level to measure the anxiety level among teachers in various districts of Manipur.
2. The study can be extended to private school teachers also.
3. The study can be extended to more items such as stress, depression which are related to anxiety.

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